

NOTES

Chemical Examination of *Salmalia malabarica* Schott & Endl. Syn. *Bombax malabaricum* Dc.

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Salmalia malabarica (Bombacaceae) is cultivated throughout the hotter parts of India. The root and bark are reported to have emetic properties¹. The investigation on the stem bark of the above plant and the isolation of Lupeol and β -sitosterol are reported in the present communication.

Dried and powdered bark (1 kg.) of *S. malabarica* was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet apparatus for 10 hrs. The crude residue (12 g.), left after solvent evaporation was separated into neutral and acidic parts by the usual procedure. The acidic part (0.33 g.) after chromatography over silica gel (10 g.) did not yield any crystalline material.

The neutral part (8.6 g.) was chromatographed over deactivated alumina (200 g.). Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and benzene (3 : 2) yielded a solid (2.41 g.) which on repeated crystallisations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol gave a crystalline compound (1.3 g.), m.p. 208–210°. Liebermann-Burchard reaction² gave a positive test for triterpenes. Acetylation of the above solid (0.25 g.) with acetic anhydride (2.5 c.c.) and pyridine (1.5 c.c.), yielded a crude acetate, which on crystallisation from methanol gave the pure acetate (0.2 g.), m.p. 212–214°. The alcohol and the acetate were identified (mixed m.p.) as lupeol and lupeol acetate respectively.

Further elution of the column with benzene gave a gummy solid (0.45 g.), which on repeated crystallisations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished a crystalline material (0.25 g.), m.p. 135–137°. Liebermann-Burchard reaction showed a positive test for sterol. Acetylation of the solid (0.2 g.) by the usual procedure followed by crystallisation yielded the pure acetate (0.1 g.), m.p. 123–124°. The sterol and the acetate were identified (mixed m.p.) as β -sitosterol and β -sitosteryl acetate respectively.

After extraction with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) the above plant material (0.5 kg.) was further extracted with rectified spirit in a soxhlet for 10 hrs. Chromatography of the crude residue obtained after solvent evaporation furnished Lupeol and β -sitosterol, identified in the same manner as described above.

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, 'Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants'. (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi), 1956, 218.
2. K. Paech and M. V. Tracey, 'Modern Methods of Plant Analysis', Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1955, 3, 64.

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